

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Characterizing Performance of a Thermal Adhesive for EV Battery Packs

The following Application Highlight addresses the measurement of both an uncured and cured thermal adhesive material using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS).

HB Fullers EV Therm 420 is described as a structural acrylic adhesive with excellent thermal conductivity and strength performance properties across a wide range of temperatures and substrates. It is a two-component mixture specified at a 10:1 volume mix ratio. In its uncured state, the material has an open time of 6-9 minutes, fixture time of 15-20 minutes and a room temperature cure time of 24 hours. In its cured state the material is specified to have a thermal conductivity greater than 1.0 W/mK.

Figure 1. HB Fuller EV Therm 420/440 used in a cell assembly (<https://chargedevs.com/apr-2022-session/stages-of-constructing-the-optimal-battery-module-architectures-utilizing-innovative-adhesive-and-sealant-solutions/>)

C-Therm’s MTPS was used to characterize performance in both the uncured and cured states. Due to the mixing requirement of the two-part system, consistency after mixing was assessed over 3 trials. The uncured, freshly mixed material was extruded directly onto the MTPS sensor, and 3 consecutive measurements were taken for each trial (n=3). As shown in figure 2 below, the material exhibited excellent consistency indicating no inhomogeneities were forming during the extrusion/mixing process of the two-components, nor were there any issues related to filler distribution. It should be noted that the curing process had not begun to any significant degree during the measurement period.

Figure 2. Sample consistency trials

The material was also characterized in its fully cured state and compared to the average of the uncured trials. The material was set in a silicon mold for >24 hours under ambient conditions at RT. Results are shown in figure 3, below. As expected, the cured material exhibited a significantly higher thermal conductivity compared to the uncured state (~37% higher). Overall, the cured sample's measured thermal conductivity of **1.462 W/mK** was in excellent agreement with the stated value on the technical data sheet.

Figure 3. Uncured vs cured thermal performance

Being able to test the uncured sample at the point of dispensing is valuable as a quality control check in understanding the consistency of component mixing and filler distribution. As the material is used in EV battery systems, this can confirm no sedimentation has occurred prior to dispensing. At this volume of material there was no indication of filler distribution/mixing issues, and the material showed excellent consistency.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com

All test data was obtained using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method under ambient conditions. Results obtained using alternative methods/test conditions may vary.